

Biocuration 2025 Workshop Summary

Collaborative Biocuration Workflows: Lessons learned from the OBO Academy

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Overview

This workshop took place as part of the Biocuration 2025 conference in Kansas City, MO, and was offered in-person and virtually. The workshop focused on the best practices for collaborative open science in advancing biocuration. With nearly 30 participants in attendance, we highlighted the lessons learned from contributing to Open Biomedical and Biological Ontology (OBO) Foundry ontologies, including the best practices that can be widely used for data standardization and annotation. We discussed the success of the OBO Academy to train ontology developers, and examined how open science principles at the core of the OBO ontologies development apply to biocuration. We also discussed some successful biocuration collaborative projects: PomBase's community curation efforts, the Gene Ontology Consortium's collaborative curation approaches, and the ACKnowledge project at Wormbase. Lastly, the importance of training resources for biocuration, the need for a more coherent and accessible system for training materials, and the potential for creating an OBO Academy-style resource for biocuration were discussed.

Key Resources

- Slides are available at: tislabs.org/collaborativebiocuration
- Access the OBO Academy materials here: <https://oboacademy.github.io/obook/>
- To join the mailing list to get updates about Monarch tutorials, go here: <https://groups.google.com/g/monarch-tutorials>

Summary of Potential Opportunities/Next Steps

As a community, we have the opportunity to work with the ISB to improve the availability of training materials for curators. Potential opportunities include:

- Create outreach packages about biocuration careers for schools and university career offices
- Expand the definition and description of biocuration on the Biocuration Society web page
- Develop an "elevator pitch" to concisely explain biocuration to non-experts
- ISB could facilitate regular (monthly or quarterly) community calls to share training opportunities and materials
- Explore creating a centralized database or GitHub resource for sharing biocuration training materials, tools, and scripts, akin to OBO Academy
- Explore partnering with platforms like Coursera to offer certified biocuration training courses

Session Overview

Collaborative Biocuration

Sabrina Toro kicked off the session with a discussion on key aspects for successful collaborative biocuration, such as transparency, openness, low barriers to participation, education, quality control, governance, and incentivization. She and Nicole Vasilevsky highlighted the OBO Ontologies development as a successful model for community involvement, particularly praising the OBO Academy for its educational resources and robust participation from both new and experienced ontology developers. The workshop aimed to promote collaborative best practices, determine needs for successful workflows, and explore the possibility of creating a Biocuration Academy similar to the OBO Academy.

OBO Academy for Ontology Development

The OBO Academy is a community resource for learning ontology development workflows, which contains a collection of training materials that are open and available to the community. The materials are organized into a centralized place, covering various aspects of ontology development, and are openly accessible through a GitHub repository. The materials are built using Markdown files and the Make Docs interface, which allows for easy editing and version control. The materials are self-guided and searchable. Monthly training sessions on specific topics are offered to the Monarch community and beyond. The OBO academy, though officially supported by the Monarch Initiative, does not “belong to” any specific individual or group. It is community-driven and community-sustained. It was highlighted that a model similar to that of the OBO academy could be applied to biocuration more generally.

PomBase Community Author Curation

Val Wood, the project manager for PomBase (an online database for fission yeast) discussed community curation. Since 2012, PomBase has engaged publication authors in curating detailed biological knowledge from their experiments. Authors have contributed nearly 26,000 curations from 1,200 publications, representing about 25% of PomBase's total curations. The curation process uses a tool called Canto, which requires no training and includes built-in constraints and checks. The quality control process involves iterative dialogue between authors and curators, combining the authors' biological expertise with the curators' ontology and biocuration best practices knowledge. Curated data is acknowledged on publication pages, featured in spotlights, and disseminated to other databases, providing benefits for both the database and the authors.

Gene Ontology Consortium's Collaborative Curation

Paul Thomas, PI of the Gene Ontology (GO) Consortium, presented collaborative curation efforts within GO. The Gene Ontology Consortium uses collaborative curation approaches to maintain and update the GO database. The consortium has a central coordination group and multiple collaborating groups, with regular in-person meetings and weekly calls to foster community building and shared goals. They use GitHub extensively for asynchronous interactions and to maintain a record of decisions. The consortium employs multiple ways for people to participate, from direct editing of the ontology by trained consortium members to suggesting changes via a Google form. Challenges include maintaining consistency across a large, diverse consortium and keeping the ontology up-to-date with new discoveries. Quality and accuracy are ensured through real-time checks in software, centralized editorial processes, automated QA processes, and informal distributed QA by consortium members.

ACKnowledge Project Improves Curation Efficiency

Kimberly Van Alken presented on the ACKnowledge project at Wormbase, which combines machine learning with community curation to improve data collection from *C. elegans* literature. The project has increased the rates of author participation in their publication curations from 20% to 44% by using automated methods to pre-populate curation forms and making the process easier for authors. The team is now working on AI-assisted fact extraction and moving the infrastructure to the Alliance of Genome Resources to handle multi-species papers. Kimberly emphasizes the importance of community involvement and relationships in maintaining knowledge bases efficiently.

Biocuration Training and Certification Discussions

Sandra Orchard and Sue Bello discussed the importance of training resources for biocuration. They highlighted the need for a more coherent and accessible system for training materials and discussed the gaps in current training offerings. The ISB is working on a survey to gather information on existing training materials and identify gaps. They also discussed the potential for creating a certification or qualification for biocuration, and the need for more outreach and recognition of the field. The conversation ended with a discussion on how to increase collaboration and reduce duplication of effort within the biocuration community.